

Railway Land Transportation Business Strategy in Indonesia

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Abstract: Railroad is one of the modes of transportation that has special characteristics and advantages. This is because the train is something that is very practical for Indonesian people in general. In addition to saving energy, trains are seen as a means of transportation for all levels of society, not only serving the upper room, providing trains also provides for the lower middle class. Data were collected using a questionnaire issued by 127 respondents provided by the Rantauprapat Great Railway Station. The data analyzed were analyzed using SEM Amos. From the results of this study the following conclusions can be drawn; service quality variables (service quality) directly affect business strategy, product attribute variables (product attributes) do not bind directly to business strategies, business strategy variables are directly bound to customer satisfaction and product attributes are directly related to customer satisfaction through business strategies.

Keywords: Business Strategy, Indonesian Railways

I. INTRODUCTION

Land transportation in Indonesia still plays a very important role in the joints of people's lives, along with the development of the land transportation era undergoes a process not only as a passenger transport but also to help the company's logistics distribution process. This has been going on since development reforms were rolled out and the need for mass and cheap modes of transportation. Since time immemorial, railways are a means of land transportation that can carry a lot of cargo, so that trains in various countries including Indonesia become trains as effective and efficient land transportation of all time, because it has the advantage of being barrier-free and has a high level of safety.

In accordance with Law No. 13 of 1992 on transportation modes, namely: railways are one of the modes of transportation that have special characteristics and advantages, especially in the ability to transport, both passengers and goods en masse, energy efficient, efficient in the use of space and have high safety factors and low pollution levels more efficient than other modes.

Labuhanbatu Regency with the capital Rantauprapat is one of the regencies located in the east coast of North Sumatra province which is located at coordinates North Latitude and East Longitude with a meter height above sea level. In addition, Labuhanbatu Regency has a strategic position that is on the east cross line of Sumatra and is at the intersection to West Sumatra and Riau, as well as connecting regional development centers in Sumatra and Java as well as having adequate access to foreign countries because it is directly bordered by coastal areas / beaches and border areas.

Besides its strategic location, Labuhanbatu regency has a high fertility rate for horticulure plantations such as oil palm and rubber. This can be seen from most of Labuhanbatu Regency surrounded by oil palm and rubber plantations either owned by companies or individuals. So this becomes the attraction of the city Rantauprapat Labuhanbatu regency because as the last stopover city of the railway line Medan - Rantauprapat. Exactly in 2018, the government planned the construction of an extended railway line to South Labuhanbatu Regency that crosses several areas between districts, with the aim of facilitating the community in individual or corporate business activities.

Looking at the growth prospects of railway transportation modes that continue to improve in increasing public satisfaction in choosing land transportation services is the main reason for this research. This study aims to measure the amount of public perception related to the attributes of products and quality of services offered by Indonesian railway companies and their influence on public loyalty, as well as provide inputs to PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) related to

improving the quality of service and public satisfaction in order to become one of the state-owned enterprises that succeed in achieving its goals.

Esmaili, Manesh and Golshan (2013) stated that the quality of service is the main weapon in maintaining satisfaction and increasing customer loyalty as service users. The increasing selectiveness of the community and the availability of alternative land transportation options illustrate that people are smart in making choices and demanding a transportation that suits their needs. Rail transportation is one of the modes of transportation that has special characteristics and advantages. This is because the train is something very practical for the people of Indonesia in general. In addition to energy saving, the railway is seen as a means of transportation for all levels of society, not only serving the upper class but also providing for the lower middle class.

II. LITERATURE

1. Product Attributes

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), that product attribute is the development of a product or service involving the benefits that the product or service will offer. Suharno and Sutarso (2010), product attributes are the development of a product needs to be done by defining the benefits to be offered, which are communicated and delivered through product attributes, such as quality, features, style and design.

2. Service Quality

Lupiyoadi and Hamdani (2008) explained that the quality of service is the extent to which the service meets its specifications. One of the service quality approaches is the SERQUAL (Service Quality) model. In short, service quality is defined as how far the difference between reality and customer expectations for the service they receive. According to Tjiptono (2011) the quality of services focuses on efforts to meet customer needs and desires as well as the accuracy of its delivery to keep up with customer expectations. There are two main factors that affect the quality of services, expected services and perceived services.

3. Business Strategy

Business strategies almost always start from what can happen and not start from what is happening. The speed of new market innovation and changes in consumer patterns require core competence. Change needs to look for competencies looking for core competencies in the business carried out. (Umar, 2003). Menururt David (2011), business strategy is a tool to achieve long-term goals. A company must strive to achieve sustainable competitive advantage, in the form of (1) continuously adapting to change in external trends and internal capacity, capabilities and resources; and (2) effective planning, implementation and evaluation of strategies that play a big role (David, 2011).

4. Customer Satisfaction

Kotler and Keller (2009) expressed satisfaction is the feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a person derived from the comparison between his impression of the performance (or results) of a product and the expectations of his expectations. Lovelock and Wright (2007) stated that, satisfaction is an emotional state, their post-purchase reaction, can be anger, dissatisfaction, annoyance, neutrality, joy and pleasure.

III. INDENTATIONS AND EQUATIONS

Concept Framework

The conceptual model of this research was built on the literature of previous research. Conceptual model of this research can be seen in Figure 1, as follows:

Figure 1. Frame of Mind

Hypothesis

H1 : service quality has a direct effect on business strategy.

H2 : Product attributes have a direct effect on business strategy.

H3 : Business strategy has a direct effect on customer satisfaction.

H4 : Product attributes directly affect customer satisfaction through business strategy.

The stages carried out in the research consist of three (3) stages, namely initial identification, data collection and data processing.

Early Identification Stage

At this stage it is divided into the following steps:

1. Observation
2. Study library
3. Identify the problem
4. Problem formulation
5. Determination of research objectives

Data Collection Stage

The types of data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data sourced directly from respondents through the results of interviews and questionnaires. As for secondary data is supporting data such as profile, history, number of customer complaints and data on number of customer complaints. As well as data collection method in this research, namely by conducting interviews, observations and questionnaires.

Population and Sample

In accordance with the purpose of problem formulation, this study selected passengers who wanted to travel rantauprapat railway station from September-December 2019 with the number of samples that returned questionnaires totaling 127 respondents. The selection of samples in this study uses purposive sampling techniques, namely passengers who have chosen rantauprapat railway transportation services.

Data Analysis

In this research, quantitative approaches are used by survey methods. Survey method is a method that uses questionnaires as a data collection tool. Quantitative approach is: Quantitative research method can be interpreted as research method based on philosophy of positivism, used to examine on certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally done randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical with the aim to test the hypothesis that has been determined (Sugiyono, 2013). Furthermore, data and facts from the collected questionnaires will be tested with Structural equation modeling (SEM).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Confirmatory Factor Analysis Of Exogenous Constructs

Diagram of the path in the CFA Model of Exogenous Construction on variable Service Quality and Product Attributes, meaning that the indicators are valid can be done further analysis:

Figure 2. CFA Model Exogenous Construction

Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Endogenous Constructs

Diagram of the path in the Endogenous Construction CFA Model on business strategy and customer satisfaction variables, meaning that the indicators are valid can be done further analysis:

Figure 3. Endogenous Construction CFA Model

Structural Equation Modelling Analysis (SEM)

The next analysis is structural equation modelling (SEM) analysis in full model (without involving invalid indicators). Analysis of data processing results at the full model stage of SEM is carried out by conducting model feasibility test and statistic test.

Table 1. Goodness Of Fit Index Results

Goodness Of Fit	CutOff Value	Results	Description
Chi-square	Expected small	81,361	Good
Probabilitas	≥ 0,05	0,211	Good
CMIN/DF	≤ 2,00	1,130	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,032	Good
AGFI	≥ 0,90	0,882	Marginal
GFI	≥ 0,90	0,919	Good
CFI	≥ 0,95	0,961	Good
TLI	≥ 0,95	0,951	Good

Source : Processed Data, 2019.

Based on Table 1, from the results of the analysis above shows that the model as a whole meets the criteria on the goodness of fit index, which means that all structural models produced are Fit models, so that it can be continued in the next analysis. The results of the presumption for full SEM model analysis based on p-value are shown in the following figure:

Figure 4. SEM output with AMOS

Hypothesis Testing

To find out the value of the relationship between constructs can be seen based on the probability value (P) in the AMOS output as shown in Figure 4. While the basis of decision making is as follows:

1. If $P > 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted.
2. If $P < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected.

From the test results of the model hypothesis that can be seen in Figure 5, it can be seen based on the model that has been analyzed using AMOS software are:

Table 2. Regression Weights

			Estima	S.E.	C.R	P	Ket
BS	<--	SQ	.494	.187	2.645	.008	Accepted
BS	<--	PA	.105	.120	.880	.379	Rejected
CS	<--	BS	.327	.146	2.236	.025	Accepted
CS	<--	PA	.255	.114	2.242	.025	Accepted

Source : Processed Data, 2019.

From the hypothetical test results in Table 2, it can be analyzed that:

1. From the test results of this first hypothesis was accepted because the parameter of estimated direct influence is 0.494 and has a significant p-value of $0.008 > 0.05$. This means that service quality variables have a direct effect on business strategy. Thus, the quality of services is the main key and this should be a priority for all state-owned companies such as PT. Indonesian Railways. The importance of services is not only understood but must be carried out on all lines of the company as a company that provides services to passengers prioritizing services in their operational activities.
2. From the test results of this second hypothesis was rejected because the parameter of estimated direct influence is 0.105 and has a significant p-value of $0.378 < 0.05$. Meaning that the product attribute variable has no direct effect on business strategy. Thus, the product attributes in this study better describe a product or service only involves the benefits that the product or service will offer. This is because the passenger is still a passenger who has the ability to pay to obtain services provided by a service company.
3. From the results of the first hypothesis test is accepted because the parameters of the estimated direct influence of 0.327 and have a significant p-value of $0.025 > 0.05$. This means that business strategy variables directly affect customer satisfaction. Thus, a business strategy can be interpreted as the direction of action or a series of decisions that help entrepreneurs in achieving certain goals and is a combination of all decisions taken from actions taken by entrepreneurs to achieve business goals and to secure competitive positions in the market by providing customer satisfaction.
4. From the test results of this first hypothesis was accepted because the parameter of estimated direct influence is 0.327 and has a significant p-value of $0.025 > 0.05$. This means that product attributes directly affect customer satisfaction through business strategies. Thus, the attributes of the products owned by PT Kereta Api Indonesia are everything that accompanies the product that is considered important by the manufacturer and consumer who are used as a differentiator and decision making on the product or the basis of the purchase decision on the product.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of this research can be concluded as follows:

1. Service quality has a direct effect on business strategy.
2. Product attribute variables have no direct effect on business strategy.
3. Business strategy variables directly affect customer satisfaction
4. Product attributes directly affect customer satisfaction through business strategies.

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